

Spectra signature assessment in relation to CDWs quality using hyperspectral imaging in VIS-NIR range

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Abstract— Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) represents an advanced and versatile technique for the analysis and discrimination of materials based on their spectral signatures, allowing the composition and purity state of a sample to be non-destructively characterized. In this work, various materials (both virgin and recycled), also conditioned by contaminants, were evaluated to understand how the presence of sodium chlorides (NaCl), sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄), and calcium sulfate (CaSO₄) can influence their spectral response and the consequent possibility of distinguishing them from the corresponding ‘pure’ reference samples. The main objective was to establish an HSI-based investigation protocol capable of highlighting even minute variations in the purity of the materials analyzed, contributing to the development of more effective quality control procedures with a view to enhancing the valorization of such materials. During the analysis, hyperspectral images were acquired in a wavelength range from 402 to 998 nm (i.e., VIS-NIR range) suitable for capturing the spectral peculiarities of the materials considered, paying particular attention to the regions where contaminants are more evident. The results showed that using this type of technology it is possible to uniquely identify each contaminant, even in small percentages, and to quantify the impact that the addition of salts such as NaCl, Na₂SO₄, and CaSO₄ exerts on the optical properties of the tested materials. Finally, the potential of HSI offers interesting prospects for the optimization of industrial processes, the verification of quality standards, and the research into innovative materials and circularity in the construction industry.

Keywords— *building life cycle, circular economy, hyperspectral imaging, materials, sensors, spectra, sustainability, vision systems, waste valorizations, construction industry.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Enhancing the durability of building materials and promoting their recovery and reuse at the end of a building life cycle is crucial from a sustainability perspective. Among the most relevant uses of characterization techniques, both traditional and innovative, the assessment of the quality of

materials in relation to their degree of purity is undoubtedly the most interesting. In particular, the analysis of contamination is fundamental not only to ensure their potential reuse, but also to promote their optimal valorization in new products. A preliminary study was carried out on the recognition and the selection of construction and demolition wastes (CDWs) with a view to create a standardized database for material management for future recycling processes involving the use of various techniques for material analysis, such as hyperspectral imaging [1]. For example, Serranti et al. [2] employed HSI-based detection instruments operating in the spectral range between 1000 and 1700 nm to identify the presence of contaminants in recycled materials. The results showed that it is possible to effectively distinguish recycled aggregates from a variety of contaminants, including bricks, gypsum, plastic, and wood, thus ensuring the quality control of the recycled materials. In the case of CDWs, the presence of various contaminants, if not correctly identified, can be particularly dangerous. Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is a traditional technique that can be used to analyze contaminants in CDWs [3]. For well and not saturated peaks, it has a wavenumber accuracy from 1.1 to 2.2 cm⁻¹ for 4 or 8 cm⁻¹ spectral resolutions, respectively. For low resolution data analyses with 16 or 32 cm⁻¹, the wavenumber accuracy is reduced to 4.7 or 10.4 cm⁻¹, respectively. Asbestos is among the most critical contaminant; indeed, when CDWs are contaminated with asbestos in unstable, dusty, or friable forms, as well as in sludge and packaging, the actual legislation (2000/532/EC2 issued by a decision of the European Commission [4]) requires that they are classified as ‘special and hazardous’, immobilized, and sent to specific landfills. Other examples of hazardous substances include chromium and lead, which are harmful both for humans and environment and require a targeted treatment before disposal. However, only non-harmful contaminants were examined within the framework of this activity. It is worth noticing that in the context of CDWs recovery processes for future use in construction, it is crucial to check for the presence of chlorides and sulfates. To this end, recycled aggregates should be subjected to specific leaching tests, aimed at measuring and verifying the compliance to the limits of sulfates and chlorides as well as other substances (such as asbestos or chromium VI). In Italy, for example, a regulation [5] was recently introduced to raise the maximum permitted limit of these compounds to

270 mg/L in eluates. The presence of chlorides represents a significant risk in reinforced concrete, as it accelerates corrosive phenomena in the reinforcing steel and, in some cases, may lead to premature failure of structures [6]. For this reason, when incorporating recycled aggregates into new reinforced concrete elements, the chloride content must not exceed the limit set by regulations. Once penetrated into mortars and concretes, chlorides can manifest themselves in two forms: as free or bound ions. Specifically, total chlorides constitute the acid-soluble fraction, while free chlorides (being soluble in water) can migrate freely and trigger the reinforcements corrosion. Consequently, bound chlorides are determined by the difference between total and free chlorides [7]. Chemically bound chlorides do not contribute significantly to the corrosion of steel reinforcement [8]; however, their binding is often partially reversible, allowing bound chlorides to dissolve in the porous solution and behave as free chlorides. The level of chemically bound chlorides in cementitious materials is closely related to the aluminate content, as AFm phases ('alumina, ferric oxide, mono-sulfate'), generated during hydration, react with chlorides to form hydrated calcium aluminate, commonly referred to as 'Friedel's salt' [9]. Recent studies have indicated that the typical absorption wavelength of the Friedel's salt is around 2260 nm, thus making its detection by NIR spectroscopy possible [10]. By analyzing the amount of the Friedel's salt present on the concrete surface, it is also possible to verify its presence in recycled concrete aggregates by means of diffuse NIR reflectance. This offers an interesting perspective for the study of chloride attack within concrete, as chloride ions tend to penetrate progressively deeper by diffusion [11]. It follows that a surface characterized by a high concentration of fixed salts may indicate the presence of a significant chloride ion content in the inner layers as well [12]. In the case of sulfate contamination, e.g., when CDWs containing gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) are landfilled, degradation in an anaerobic environment can occur, leading to the formation of gaseous hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), which is responsible for environmental problems due to its toxicity and strong smell. Furthermore, H_2S can contribute to air pollution and lead to negative effects on human health, making proper management and disposal of gypsum waste crucial to reduce its environmental impact [13]. On the other hand, sodium sulfates react with cement hydration products (calcium hydroxide, calcium silicate hydrate - C-S-H - and calcium silicate aluminate - C-A-H), generating expansion and cracking linked to the formation of ettringite and gypsum. It can also cause softening and disintegration phenomena due to the alteration of C-S-H [14], known as 'thaumasite' formation, in particular situations (cold and humid environments - temperature $< 10^\circ\text{C}$ and RH $> 95\%$ - and the presence of CaCO_3 finely dispersed in the cement paste). On the other hand, magnesium sulfates originate layers of brucite ($\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$) and gypsum on the surface of the concrete; in parallel, in the adjacent transition zone, the C-S-H phase undergoes calcium depletion, weakening the overall structure and compromising the durability of the material, with the consequent risk of concrete degradation [14]. Another non-damaging contamination, which affects the properties of the new cementitious materials after recycling CDW aggregates, is the presence of adhering hydrated paste in the surroundings of the aggregates. This increases the porosity of the final material, in turn promoting water absorption and reducing mechanical strength.

The aim of this research work is to propose a methodology for assessing the quality of materials of interest through

spectral signature using hyperspectral imaging in the VIS-NIR range. The *Introduction* section explains the current state of the art in this field, the *Material and Methods* section presents the measurement protocol and the data analysis procedures. The *Proof of Concept* section reports the results obtained from the acquisition and analysis. Finally, the *Conclusions* section outlines the final considerations on this research study.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Sample preparation

Three different contaminants (i.e., sodium chlorides, sodium chloride sulfates, and calcium sulfates (i.e. gypsum)) were chosen to evaluate the possibility of identifying them in aggregate materials. In particular, two types of pure materials were screened, namely a calcareous aggregate produced by Esinca S.r.l. (Serra San Quirico, Italy, <https://esinca.com/>), labelled as 'NA' (Natural Aggregate), and a Recycled Concrete Aggregate produced by E-LAB S.r.l. (Vallemare, Italy, <https://www.e-lab.srl/>), labelled as 'RCA', both with a maximum diameter (D_{max}) of 8 mm. In order to avoid possible influences caused by the presence of moisture, the aggregates were first oven-dried at 100°C until they reached a constant mass; then, they were analyzed 'as is' (3 acquisitions were performed for each sample, considering 3 NA samples and 3 RCA samples, for a total of 18 acquisitions) in order to derive the representative spectrum of each material. Subsequently, 3 different samples belonging to each aggregate type were contaminated as follows:

- n. 1 was immersed for 2 weeks in a chloride-rich solution consisting of 3.5 wt% NaCl (commonly used in literature to simulate seawater [15]);
- n. 1 was immersed for 2 weeks in a sulfate-rich solution consisting of 14 wt% Na_2SO_4 ;
- n. 1 was contaminated with 10% CaSO_4 powder by mass.

Subsequently, the samples were oven-dried again at 100°C until constant mass was obtained to avoid any influence due to the presence of water and tested again using the HSI technique; 3 repeated acquisitions were performed for each sample (n. 1 NA - NaCl sample, n. 1 NA - Na_2SO_4 sample, n. 1 RCA - CaSO_4 sample, n. 1 NA - NaCl sample, n. 1 RCA - Na_2SO_4 sample, n. 1 RCA - CaSO_4 sample), for a total of 18 acquisitions. In Section B. *Hyperspectral system and analysis* the acquisition procedure and equipment required to analyze the spectra of the materials are described. Data processing, described in Section C. *Data processing* was performed by averaging the spectra obtained from the repeated acquisitions and calculating the standard deviation for each group of interest in order to obtain the related confidence interval.

B. Hyperspectral system and data acquisition

The analysis steps for each sample are listed below and the measurement chain is explained in detail and summarised in the pipeline in Fig. 1.

Sample preparation and acquisition bench. The sample to be analyzed was selected, cleaned, and brought to the workbench. The workbench was cleaned to remove any residue left by the previous sample; hence, the new sample to be examined was placed on the test table.

Preparation of the acquisition system. The 4250 V-NIR camera (Hinalea) [16] was connected to the computer and switched on; the camera native software, i.e., Hinalea APP (Hinalea) [16], was opened.

Black calibration. Black calibration was carried out using the Hinalea APP, keeping the camera lens covered with its own cover. This step was not repeated for every measurement since black is calibrated only once.

Cooling and lighting. The cooling system consisting of three Peltier modules with fans and aluminium heat exchangers, which were operated by a Peltier cell controller (Fig. 2) connected to the insulating container via a thermocouple, was switched on. The system temperature must always be maintained in the range $(20 \pm 5) ^\circ\text{C}$. The halogen lamp lighting system is represented in Fig. 2; after switching on, it was connected to the external power supply, which makes the lighting stable.

Focusing and white calibration. The specimen to be examined was focused by adjusting the camera lens; then, the white target was positioned at the same height as the specimen, thus maintaining the focus. An auto-exposure was then performed to adjust the illumination and avoid saturating the image during the acquisition phase; white calibration was then performed using the Hinalea APP. This step, unlike black calibration, must be repeated each time the focus of the sample under analysis is changed.

Sample acquisition. The white target was removed and the sample to be analysed was positioned; further self-exposure was performed. The sample was acquired using the Hinalea APP; this step took approximately 1-2 minutes. Three repeated acquisitions were performed on each sample in order to have more data to work with and to check the repeatability of the information derived from the measurement.

Saving the data for post-processing. The data were processed through the dedicated software, which produced the hypercube; reflectance was taken as the relevant data. The Hinalea APP also allows us to select a ROI (Region Of Interest) and to export the reflectance spectrum of the selected region in a .txt file, much less heavy and more manageable than the hypercube.

The data obtained from the hyperspectral camera measurements were processed by writing a dedicated software using the Python programming language.

C. Data processing

The first step was to import the previously acquired spectral data into the code and calculate the mean and

Fig. 2. Hyperspectral data acquisition pipeline.

standard deviation values of the spectra of each sample (per each wavelength considered in the range, with a resolution of 4 nm). The averages were calculated by summing the reflectance values for each wavelength from 402 to 998 nm and dividing the total by the number of acquisitions of each sample (i.e., 3). The standard deviation was calculated to determine the dispersion of the data around the averaged spectrum curve, providing an indication of the variability and the repeatability of previous measurements for each sample. The formulas used to calculate the mean and standard deviation are given in Equation (1) and Equation (2), respectively. This was done in order to have a clear idea of the material characterization for each macro class in terms of the variability of the spectra and, therefore, to correctly interpret the results.

$$\bar{x}_\lambda = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_{i,\lambda} \quad (1)$$

where:

- \bar{x}_λ is the mean spectrum;
- N is the number of total samples considered for the computation of the mean spectrum;
- $x_{i,\lambda}$ sample spectrum at index i .

$$\sigma_\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_{i,\lambda} - \bar{x}_{i,\lambda})^2} \quad (2)$$

where:

- σ_λ is the standard deviation;
- N is the number of total samples considered for the computation of the standard deviation;
- $x_{i,\lambda}$ sample spectrum at index i ;
- $\bar{x}_{i,\lambda}$ is the mean spectrum at index i .

III. PROOF OF CONCEPT

This section will present the results obtained from the analysis of the samples and the comparison of the different spectral signatures.

Specifically, Fig. 3 shows the comparison between the standard deviation filled area and the mean spectrum in continuous line (red for RCA samples, blue for NA samples), as the standard deviations are not appreciable from the graphs, the maximum standard deviation values for the different specimens are given in Table 1. The plots reported in Fig. 3 present the mean and standard deviation values related to: Uncontaminated natural specimens, (NA 3 specimens, 3

Fig. 1. Peltier conditioning system and halogen lamp illumination.

Fig. 3. Comparison between non-contaminated samples NA and RCA (top/bottom left) with respect to NA and RCA contaminated with CaSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , NaCl , in second, third, and fourth columns, respectively; mean spectrum is reported with a solid line, while respective colored area refers to confidence interval given by $\mu \pm \sigma$. Zoomed portions are reported for the sake of readability.

acquisition per specimen type – first figure, top); uncontaminated recycled specimens, (RCA 3 specimens, 3 acquisition per specimen type – first figure, bottom); contaminated with CaSO_4 natural specimens, (NA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – second figure top); contaminated with CaSO_4 recycled specimens, (RCA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – second figure, bottom); contaminated with Na_2SO_4 natural specimens, (NA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – third figure, top); contaminated with Na_2SO_4 recycled specimens, (RCA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – third figure, bottom); contaminated with NaCl natural specimens, (NA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – fourth figure, top); contaminated with NaCl recycled specimens, (RCA 1 specimen, 3 acquisition per specimen type – fourth figure, bottom);

It is evident that the spectra between NA and RCA are different, even in absence of contaminants, for not only are the reflectance values in NA samples higher than RCA samples in the range between 592 to 998 nm, but also for the different signatures of the spectra. With the addition of contaminants, the characteristic signature of each spectrum is even more evident and is also amplified by the additional contribution due to the chemicals; this can be clearly observed especially in the 400-500 nm range and at 600 nm.

Error! Reference source not found. shows the overall comparison among the spectra related to the natural samples (NA) (mean and standard deviation reported in black, solid line and coloured area, respectively, based on 9 acquisition trials on 3 samples), to the NaCl -contaminated sample (mean and standard deviation reported in pink, solid line and coloured area, respectively, of 3 repeated acquisition trials on n. 1 NA sample), to the Na_2SO_4 -contaminated sample (mean and standard deviation reported in indigo, solid line and coloured area, respectively, of n. 3 acquisition trials obtained on n. 1 NA sample), and the CaSO_4 -contaminated sample (mean and standard deviation reported in cyan, solid line and coloured area, respectively, of n. 3 acquisition trials on n. 1 NA sample).

Among NA samples, it is still possible to discriminate curves characterized by each contaminant both among

themselves and with respect to the reference spectrum in the range of 400-500 nm and based on the different slope starting from 500 nm. The spectral behaviour is similar at some points between the NaCl -contaminated specimen and the Na_2SO_4 -contaminated specimen; hence, it could be difficult to discriminate between the two types of contaminants. Fig. 5 describes the global comparison of natural samples (RCA), considered as the reference sample (black curves, with mean and standard deviation computed on 9 repeated tests on 3 samples), NaCl -contaminated sample (pink curves, with mean and standard deviation computed on 3 repeated tests), Na_2SO_4 -contaminated sample (indigo curves, with mean and standard deviation computed on 3 repeated tests), CaSO_4 -contaminated sample (cyan curves, mean and standard on 3 repeated tests). Among RCA samples, it is still possible to discriminate curves characterized by each contaminant both among themselves and with respect to the reference spectrum in the range of 400-500 nm and based on the different slope starting from 500 nm. The spectral behaviour is similar at some points between the NaCl -contaminated specimen and the Na_2SO_4 -contaminated specimen. Hence, the considerations are similar to those made for NA samples.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work evaluates the applicability and the potentiality of hyperspectral imaging (HSI) techniques in evaluating the quality of virgin/recycled aggregates to be recycled or reused in construction with a perspective of enhancing the circularity in the construction industry. In particular, different contaminants have been considered, namely sodium chlorides, sodium sulphate, and calcium sulphate. Repeated measurements were performed in order to evaluate also the effect of the variability of the samples and the repeatability of the measurement procedure itself. The results show that,

TABLE 1. STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Sample type	Standard deviation (max values)			
	Not contaminated	CaSO_4	Na_2SO_4	NaCl
NA	0.020	0.002	0.017	0.028
RCA	0.0148	0.000	0.019	0.015

Fig. 4. Global comparison (mean and standard deviation) of natural samples (NA, non-contaminated, black – 9 repeated tests), NaCl-contaminated sample (pink – 3 repeated tests), Na₂SO₄-contaminated sample (indigo – 3 repeated tests), CaSO₄-contaminated sample (cyan – 3 repeated tests).

especially in certain spectral regions (namely 400-500 nm and at 600 nm), it is possible to discriminate between natural and contaminated samples as well as among diverse contaminants, being the aggregates virgin or recycled. Hence, HSI proved to be effective in the material quality assessment and can be exploited for the characterization of CDWs and for their evaluation in terms of quality, and, hence, reusability.

The limits of the present study can be identified in the limited number of samples analysed as well as the types of contaminants. In fact, it is evident how the variability of materials and contaminants is crucial in this analysis and for a hypothetical generation of datasets for AI models for classification purposes. In future, it would be interesting to extend the analysis to different types of CDWs, also increasing the size of the test population as well as having a complete dataset including the variability of the materials of interest allowing for the generation of more robust models capable of recognising a wider range of materials and contaminants. Additionally, the continuous technological development of sensing technologies could allow the realisation of efficient systems at low cost; special attention should be paid to boundary conditions, such as lighting and ambient temperature, which could influence the success of the test; these factors should be thoroughly taken into account during the system development phase to maximize the quality of data.

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Fig. 5. Global comparison (mean and standard deviation) of natural samples (RCA, non-contaminated, black – 9 repeated tests), NaCl-contaminated sample (pink – 3 repeated tests), Na₂SO₄-contaminated sample (indigo – 3 repeated tests), CaSO₄-contaminated sample (cyan – 3 repeated tests).

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